

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

A case study of a pet dog bitten by snake (cobra) healed successfully and brought to life by Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) energy healing

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Abstract

Introduction: Animals too have an Aura similar to humans and their energy field can be healed by trained energy healers, to treat any illnesses in the physical body. Pet animals, like dogs, experience snake bites sometimes, needing emergency treatment. This paper presents a case of a snake bitten dog successfully healed and fully recovered by using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing protocols.

Methods: This paper uses case study method collecting patient data before and after healing, and details of YPV intervention applied by a trained healer for treating this animal patient.

Results: After two days of healing, the dog could get up and eat food. Within 15 days of healing, the wound near mouth got healed fully and healing continued on hard mass at mouth area and wound below leg. After 45 days of healings, the dog got completely healed and the hard mass near mouth came out.

Conclusions: As an integrated and holistic system, the YPV system of healing has been found to be less expensive modality without the use of any medications and without touching the animal patient as well as human patient. YPV healing offers great opportunity to address snake bitten cases with successful results Further research may be conducted on the characteristics of the energy body of animals to throw more light for effective healing taking lesser time.

Keywords: Yoga Prana Vidya ®; YPV ®; snake bite; Healing animals

1. Introduction

1.1. Energy healing of animals

The aura field, which is also known as bio-plasmic body, is a field of energy surrounding and interpenetrating the physical body. Animals too, like people, have an aura (see figure 1). It contains, supports and protects the rest of the energy anatomy, and provides a strong boundary between the individual's energy and the rest of the world [1].

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1.1.1. Aura of a dog

(Picture source: pranichealingofanimals.com)

Figure 1 Diagrammatic representation of aura of a dog

Animals serve many roles when it comes to energy and the planet. Their energy fields are far more expansive than ours (as always associated with their Group). For example, a dog's energy field is several times that of a human. A horse's field will encompass a large arena, and a cat's aura will fill an entire property. The energy of wildlife is especially important to the survival of the planet. They create a frequency that maintains the vibrational health of the planet, and all creatures on it [2].

Animals function from instinct, which is a form of energy. In addition to their heightened senses of sight, hearing and smell, they sense what is all around them. It is as if they have radar at the edges of their field [2]. They have emotional and psychological lives too, and they can be affected by the energies they encounter in the world, just like humans are. Energy work on animals is based on the same principles as that applies to humans, recognizing that they have a physical body and also an energy body.

When cats and dogs are surrounded by stressful situations, negative energies can accumulate, causing imbalance and/or congestion in their energetic body that is reflected in the physical body as what are known as 'symptoms.'

An animal energy healer works with Energy healing modalities to help balance the systems of energy throughout an animal's body to alleviate stress, ailments, and disease. Experience shows that skilled practitioners work with animal patients experiencing a wide range of physical, psychological, and emotional symptoms, including for example, fears/phobias, separation anxiety, trauma response, nervousness/general anxiety, aggression, travel anxiety and motion sickness, stress and irritability, grief over the loss of a person or animal friend, phobias, obsessions and compulsions, depression, musculoskeletal issues, decreased mobility, nervous system disorders etc. [3].

The Aura of every living organism is surrounded by an electromagnetic energy field. This field vibrates at different frequencies with bands of colors and reflects our state of mind, body and inner being. Every color has a different vibrational frequency and is associated with various chakras or energy centres in your body. Our Aura colors are determined by physical, mental, emotional and spiritual states of being [4].

1.2. Snakebite in Animals

Snake bite in animals generally occurs during grazing or hunting or while playing in the garden. Most of the cases reported of snake bite occurred in dogs and horses which created an emergency resulting from poisoning from snake venom, and required immediate attention. Inadequate treatment may lead to untoward consequences.[5] Animals exhibit various symptoms like cardio pulmonary dysfunction, local tissue damage, blood coagulation defects, ataxia etc, depending on type of snake bite. Anandam et al. [5] opined that systemic sign can vary and may include hypotension, shock, cardiac arrhythmias, bleeding disorders, ptyalism, nausea, vomiting, respiratory distress, mental confusion, rhabdomyolysis, and the acute renal failure.

Snake bite in animals may cause swelling around the bite, wounds, bleeding from the wound, pain and may lead to infection after some time by non-venomous snake bite (Pythons, King snakes etc). Venomous snake bite may cause tissue damage and bleeding from the wound, vomiting, dilated pupil, breathing problem, blood in urine, immobility,

paralysis, collapse and may cause death. The reaction to the bite depends on species, size of snake, amount of venom and site of the bite.

Non venomous bite can be treated with antibiotics, anti-inflammatory drugs required to address the symptoms. Venomous bite treatment includes anti venom, antihistamines drugs required to treat the symptoms depends upon severity along with cleaning the bite. Recovery depends upon age, size and current health status of the dog [6].

1.3. Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV System)

Yoga Prana Vidya is an integrated and holistic system of healing and treatment. YPV is based on ancient art and science of Pranic Energy Healing, and experience gained from decades of practice shows that this system has successfully healed and treated various types of diseases and illnesses as a complementary or alternative medicine for not only humans but some pet animals also. Literature shows that more than 30 research articles on successful applications of YPV healing of humans have been published and more will appear regularly in published literature. It is noted that published successful case reports include, treatment of difficult medical cases [7], Diabetes management & control [8], removing arterial block in heart without surgery [9], vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp [10], improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme [11], Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency [12], improvements of health and immunity of senior citizens [13], speedy recovery of COVID patients [14], treatment of hypothyroidism [15], Lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children [16], saving life of a snake-bitten human female [17], improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children [18], managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy [19], healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [20]. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [21], and significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [22].

Figure 2 Pictures of human aura taken with GDV camera

The process of applying healing energy consists of cleansing the energy body with sensitized hands by a trained and skilled healer, and in the next step energizing the body and the affected part of the body with fresh Pranic energy. Advanced techniques of color prana are also used for faster healing. Figure 2 shows pictures of human aura taken using a GDV camera, and the differences in the energy body before and after healing are clearly evident.

2. Case report

2.1. Before YPV Healing

A 5-year-old Dalmatian dog was bitten by a snake (cobra), the snake bites were found one near the mouth and the other below the front leg {see figures 3 (a), (b)}. The owner took the dog to pet clinic in 45 min time, by that time swelling

started, doctor did first aid, provided medication and informed that the dog may not survive. Owner continued to provide dressing the wound (only cleaning) for next 2 days in the same clinic. Day by day, the dog's condition was getting worse, and it was unable to walk, feeling dull and inactive, and was not eating any food.

That's the time the dog's owner contacted the YPV healer and shared the details and requested if anything can be done from healing point of view, for which the healer explained about YPV and started healing for this special case.

A

B

Figure 3 Photos showing snakebite wounds on mouth and right leg

2.2. Healing protocols used

During the healing process, the energy body of the dog was cleansed with brilliant violet prana and green prana followed by cleansing whole body parts with green and violet prana. Then the affected parts were treated. Affected parts (wound near mouth and below the leg) were localised with blue prana and then cleansed with green and orange prana. After cleansing, the affected parts were energised with greenish blue and violet prana to reduce infection in starting later on with green and red to heal the wound. The hard mass area near mouth was localised with blue and cleansed with green and orange using soaking technique. After cleansing it was energised with brilliant violet prana to dissolve the hard mass. Everyday 20 minutes of healing was given to the dog after washing the wound for about 45 days.

2.3. After YPV Healing

Healing improvements could be seen in the dog within few healings. The area of the wound got infected and liquid was formed. The owner himself started cleaning the wounds every day. There was also a hard mass formed near mouth area. As healing continued day by day improvements had taken place. Within the next 2 days of healing, the dog got up to have food. The owner was so much happy to see the dog able to walk to have food. Owner got hopes that it will survive, healing continued everyday including cleaning of the infected area. Dog became active, started playing, no other medication was given to the dog except cleaning the wound.

Figure 4 Images after full healing of wounds

Within 15 days, the wound near mouth got healed fully and healing continued on hard mass at mouth area and wound below leg. After 45 days of healings the dog got completely healed and the hard mass near mouth came out. {See images in figure 4 (a) (b) (c)}

3. Discussion

In the present case study, the venomous dog showed clinical signs such as dullness, depression, staggering gait, oozing of blood from bitten area and edematous face. This was also in agreement with Anandam et al [5], who reported salivation, dullness, muscular weakness with abnormal gait. These clinical signs can be attributed to the enzymatic and non-enzymatic compounds in the snake venom. In another case of a human female bitten by a venomous snake, YPV healing successfully treated the patient who recovered fully within 15 days [17]. YPV healing offers great opportunity to address snake bitten cases with successful results. It is also observed in this case that the loving care and bond between the owner and the animal also played a prominent role in the overall recovery process of the animal.

4. Conclusion

As an integrated and holistic system, the YPV system of healing has been found to be less expensive modality without the use of any medications and without touching the animal patient as well as human patient. The potential of YPV system of healing for multidisciplinary collaboration and rigorous research in cases of this kind is certainly promising. Physicists, neuroscientists, psychologists, social workers, life coaches, veterinarians and animal behaviourists will be able to aid in the understanding of the human-animal bond, as well as develop a model for energy healing interaction.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors.

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